

FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS OF BEARING STRENGTH OF STITCHED LAMINATES WITH SINGLE JOINT

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SUMMARY: A three-dimensional finite element model was developed to investigate the bearing properties of mechanically fastened joints in unstitched and stitched uniweave T300/QY9512 laminates. Hashin's three-dimensional failure criterion was used to predict the progressive ply failure. Stitching node position effect was of primary interest. A good agreement between experimental results and numerical predictions was observed. The results show that the bearing strength decreased when the stitching node position was close to the hole boundary.

KEYWORDS: stitched laminates, stitching node position, finite element model, bearing strength; contact law.

INTRODUCTION

The use of stitched laminates to strengthen aeronautic and astronautic engineering structures has been extensive over the past decade. Although the stitching may replace mechanical fasteners such as rivets and bolts in some area, the mechanically fastened joints were inevitable in some applications, such as skin-to-spar and tail-to-fuselage connections. However, few researchers had studied the bearing strength of stitched laminates with single joint [1, 2]. In this paper, a three-dimensional finite element model is developed for predicting stress distributions near the edge of bolt hole for some typical stitching node positions. Hashin's three-dimensional failure criterion [3] is used to estimate the damage initiation and damage propagation at each ply. The model was also used to predict the bearing strength of bolted unstitched and stitched laminates, the effect of stitching direction, stacking sequence and stitching node position were considered. A series of load-displacement curves were drawn from the numerical calculation and compared with the ones obtained from the experimental researches in this paper.

MODEL DEVELOPMENT

In order to take into account the three-dimensional stress state at the hole boundary, the effects of stacking sequence and through-thickness pressure, three-dimensional model is required for the mechanically fastened joints in unstitched and stitched laminates. And in order to predict damage initiation and growth, which is essential for assessing the

performance of the joints and design with safety, progressive damage modeling techniques (PDM) must be resorted. The PDM comprises the components of stress analysis, failure analysis and material property degradation [4, 5].

In this paper, a three-dimensional finite element model is created to simulate a mechanically fastened joint in a stitched laminate. Linear eight-node isoparametric solid elements are used to model each ply of the laminate. This technique allows computing the stress in each ply so that propagation of damage from ply-to-ply can be studied. And this type of element assures that the contact forces are consistent with the contact direction and provides a reasonable approximation of the through-thickness stresses [1, 2]. Moreover, three-dimensional beam elements are developed to model stitches as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Scheme of 3-D beam element

To simulate the effect of stitches on the inter-plane properties of composites laminates, functions of elastics matrix are used in the finite element analysis. Assume that the fibres are arranged as sine or cosine curves along x-axis and distributed regularly along y-axis; the areas of stitching node are filled with matrix. Figure 2 shows the scheme of a typical status, which stitching direction is perpendicular to the ply orientation angle. The fibres fluctuating functions among the whole ply could be expressed as below:

Figure 2. Stitching direction is perpendicular to the ply orientation angle

$$\varphi(x, y) = \begin{cases} a \left[1 - M\left(\frac{y}{w}\right) \right] \sin\left(\frac{2\pi x}{l} - \frac{\pi}{2}\right) & \{2nw \leq y < (2n+1)w\} \\ -M\left(\frac{y}{w}\right) a \sin\left(\frac{2\pi x}{l} - \frac{\pi}{2}\right) & \{(2n+1)w \leq y < 2nw\} \end{cases} \quad n = 0, 1, 2 \dots \quad (1)$$

w being half of the stitching steps, l the space between two parallel stitching lines. a the radius of stitching threads; $M\left(\frac{y}{w}\right)$ the remainder of $\frac{y}{w}$.

The angle β from a point on fibre to x-axis is defined by:

$$\beta = \begin{cases} \tan^{-1} \left[\frac{2\pi a}{l} \left(1 - M \left(\frac{y}{w} \right) \right) \cos \left(\frac{2\pi x}{l} - \frac{\pi}{2} \right) \right] & \{2nw \leq y < (2n+1)w\} \\ \tan^{-1} \left[-M \left(\frac{y}{w} \right) \frac{2\pi a}{l} \cos \left(\frac{2\pi x}{l} - \frac{\pi}{2} \right) \right] & \{(2n+1)w \leq y < 2nw\} \end{cases} \quad n = 0, 1, 2 \dots \quad (2)$$

For the fibres are distributed regularly along y-axis, a relationship between the fibre volume fraction of the whole lay V_f and x is proposed as:

$$V_f(x) = \frac{V_f^* w}{w - a \sin \left(\frac{2\pi x}{l} - \frac{\pi}{2} \right) - a} \quad (3)$$

V_f^* being the fibre volume fraction of unstitched laminates.

Based on the function of fibre volume fraction after fibre bending, the relationships between elastic properties and x are proposed as:

$$\begin{aligned} E_1(x) &= E_f V_f(x) + E_m [1 - V_f(x)]; & E_2(x) &= \frac{E_f E_m}{E_f [1 - V_f(x)] + E_m V_f(x)} \\ \nu_{12}(x) &= \nu_f V_f(x) + \nu_m [1 - V_f(x)]; & G_{12}(x) &= \frac{G_f G_m}{G_f [1 - V_f(x)] + G_m V_f(x)} \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Then, the stiffness matrix after fibre bending is represented by:

$$[\bar{C}] = [T][C][T]^T \quad (5)$$

$[C]$ being the stiffness matrix, $[T]$ the stress-strain matrix. Both of them are varied by the change of in-plane coordinates x and y .

The same rule could be seen in the other ply orientation angles and other stitching direction. 12 groups of element stiffness matrix are developed, considered 0° , 90° , 45° , -45° plies and 0° , 90° , 45° stitching directions. In addition, the effect of different stitching node positions on relative formula is solved by coordinate movement. In this way, the whole model of stitched laminates is developed.

The bolt is modeled as a rigid body, because the elasticity of the bolt does not have a significant effect on the stress distribution around the hole boundary [1, 2]. The contact algorithm is based on a master-slave approach where the nodes on the master surface (bolt surface) can penetrate slave segments (laminates hole) [1, 2]. The value of the clearance is used to check the contact status when the stitched laminate is loaded. If penetration is detected, the contact algorithm enforced a constraint. If no penetration is detected, no constraint is applied. Hashin's three-dimensional failure criterion is used to predict damage onset and type within a ply [5]. Each of the damage modes is predicted respectively. When damage occurs, the associated material properties must be modified according to the type of damage. For example, when matrix cracking or shear cracking is detected in an element, E_2 , G_{12} , G_{23} are modified; when fibre fracture is predicted, E_1 is reduced.

EXPERIMENT

The materials selected for this study was Uniweave T300/QY9512 Laminates made by RFI. For the stitched laminates, Kevlar-29 untwist roving of 1400 denier was employed to provide the through-thickness reinforcement of the laminates. The material of the bolt was

30CrMnSiA. And the test conditions were 25°C/dry, 25°C/wet and 130°C/wet, respectively. The wet environment was to dip the specimens in 71°C±10°C distilled water for 340 hours.

The stacking sequence for the specimens (stitched and unstitched laminates) were [45/0/-45/90]_{2S}, [0/45/0/-45/90/-45/0/45/0]_S and [45/0/-45/90/45/90/-45/0/45]_S, respectively. The stitching directions were 0°, 45° and 90°, respectively. The stitching steps were always at 5 mm. The spaces between two parallel stitching lines were 5 mm in width. Each specimen was 150 mm long and 40 mm wide. The nominally thickness of unstitched laminates was 2 mm and 2.25 mm, respectively. The thickness increase of stitched specimens was less than 5%. Hole with a diameter of 6 mm was drilled. The distance between the hole and the free edge of the plate was 20 mm. The specimen geometry is illustrated in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Specimen geometry

The specimens were loaded using an MTS880-50kN test machine. Three tests were performed for each sort of specimen in order to obtain the average value for bearing strength. For the same stacking sequence, stitching direction and test condition, three specimens had different stitching node position around the hole boundary. From the load-displacement curves of the bolted unstitched and stitched laminates, the following parameters were obtained: initial bearing strength, 4% hole deformation bearing strength and ultimate bearing strength. When the first load drop-off occurred, the relative stress was defined as the initial bearing strength. Since there were lots of factors exist in the tests, the discussions of experimental results in this paper were mainly based on the initial bearing strength.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To predict a correct joint strength, the model should first predict an accurate stress distribution around the hole. Figure 4 show two typical stitching node positions which were used in numerical calculation. The circumferential co-ordinate θ is shown in Figure 5.

Figure 4. Scheme of stitching node position near the hole boundary:
 (a) Stitching node position is away from the hole boundary;
 (b) Stitching node position is close to the hole boundary.

Figure 5. Definition of angle θ

The hole-holt contact problem is highly non-linear with the stress distribution changing as the load and contact surface are increased. The radial compressive stresses σ_{rr} and through-thickness direct stresses σ_{zz} are normalized with the bearing stress for an applied load of 3500 N. The load level was selected to ensure that the stress levels were compared at a point where the material remained undamaged.

For stitched laminates with stacking sequences $[45/0/-45/90]_{2S}$ and 0° stitching direction, normalized radial compressive stresses σ_{rr} along the hole boundary obtained by the current model are illustrated in Figure 6. The magnitude and distribution of stresses at the hole boundary (especially near the region $\theta = 0^\circ$) was found to be dependent on the level of stitching node position. When the stitching node position is away from the hole boundary (stitching node position is A), σ_{rr} are lower than that of the unstitched laminates. But, when the stitching node position is close to the hole boundary (stitching node position is B), σ_{rr} are mainly equal to that of the unstitched laminates, and near the region $\theta = 0^\circ$, σ_{rr} are greatly higher than that of the unstitched laminates. The normalized radial compressive stresses distributions of laminates with 45° and 90° stitching direction follow the same trends, as shown in Figure 7 and Figure 8.

Figure 6. Radial stress distribution around hole boundary (0° stitching direction)

Figure 7. Radial stress distribution around hole boundary (45° stitching direction)

Figure 8. Radial stress distribution around hole boundary (90° stitching direction)

The radial compressive stresses at the bearing plane ($\theta = 0^\circ$) are shown to increase significantly as the stitching node position was close to the hole boundary. The comparison of maximum of radial compressive stresses with different stitching node position is shown in Figure 9. When the stitching node position is away from the hole boundary, the maximum of σ_{rr} is slightly lower than that of unstitched laminates; but, when the stitching node position is close to the hole boundary, the maximum of σ_{rr} is greatly higher than that of unstitched laminates. The numerical results illustrate the stitching node position significantly affects the bearing failure of bolted stitched laminates.

The through-thickness stresses at the hole boundary contributes significantly to the bearing failure of the laminates. The distributions of through-thickness direct stresses σ_{zz} and on the 90°/45° interface are shown in Figure 10. The great variation of σ_{zz} also occurs near the bearing plane ($\theta = 0^\circ$). The close stitching node position causes obvious high through-thickness direct stress.

The results show that the magnitude and distribution of stress at the hole boundary are significantly dependent on the stitching node position. With the distance between the stitching node position and the hole boundary decreases, both the in-plane and out-of-plane stress levels increase greatly. And the earlier initiation of damage in the stitched laminates could be suppressed when the radial compressive stress and through-thickness direct stress in the bearing plane decrease.

Figure 9. Comparison of the maximum of radial compressive stress

Figure 10. Through-thickness direct stress distribution around hole boundary

Figure 11, 12 and 13 show the load-displacement relations obtained in the experimental tests (converted from the original $P - \delta$ curves) and the load-displacement relation obtained using the numerical model for the unstitched and stitched laminates.

Figure 11. Experimental and numerical load-displacement relations for unstitched laminates

Figure 12. Experimental and numerical load-displacement relations for stitched laminates (stitching node position is A)

Figure 13. Experimental and numerical load-displacement relations for stitched laminates (stitching node position is B)

The experimental and predicted failure loads are presented in Table 1. The value of predicted initial failure load agrees very well with the experimental results. The comparison shows that the stitching node position affects the bearing properties of stitched laminates with single-lap single-bolt joint configuration greatly. Furthermore, the 3D FE model developed in this paper simulates progressive damage and predicts strength very well.

Table 1. Comparison between experimental and predicted bearing strength

Specimen	Experimental initial failure load / N	Experimental ultimate failure load / N	FE model predicted failure load / N	Error / %
Unstitched	5975	11250	6200	3.8%
Stitching node position is A	8050	12375	6800	15.5%
Stitching node position is B	7250	11200	6000	17.2%

CONCLUSION

The three-dimensional model developed in this paper consists of the following two major components: stress analysis and strength prediction. The numerical model takes into account the contact problem and provides a reliable method of stress analysis, including the out-of-plane stress components which are usually neglected. The non-critical damage mechanisms occurring in the matrix and fibres are predicted using Hashin's three-dimensional failure criterion. The failure strength predicted by this model is within 20% of the experimental data.

The effect of stitching node position is found to be important both from the experimental and numerical research. When the stitching node position is away from the hole boundary, the bearing strength of stitched laminates is higher than that of unstitched laminates; when the stitching node position is close to the hole boundary, its bearing strength declines greatly, even lower than that of unstitched laminates.

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